

>>"What makes a good philosophy, Shifu?" ~15 year old student at Wu-Tao-Di Academy

In this letter:

- The 3 requirements of a good philosophy
- MIMS as a MIMS
- Standards, evolution, and expansion of the MIMS
- Introducing the Altstream Heat Test

MIMS 1.01-.03: the Philosophy Integration Self-test

Unsurprisingly, due to the self-rigor, MIMS philosophy is itself a MIMS

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Re: Is MIMS a “good” philosophy to study? Is it useful?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

A young, deeply thoughtful and even *intrepid* student of mine asked me about “what makes a good philosophy.” I told him it took 3 things.

MIMS 1.02 - Good Philosophy

A good philosophy is defined first by determining what is good and what is bad, and then there are clearly three forms/factors which matter. This isn't Philosophy 101 class, we are interested in results.

- ★ Good is defined as that which is harmonious and wholesome for the recipient entity, which accords with a grander design in alignment with the “Big G” shape/form/structure.
- ★ Bad is its dual opposite.
- ★ Typically this is manifested as a fact of health and/or survival and evolution.¹

Therefore we can see what the three things must be:

1. A good philosophy must be internally self-consistent
2. A good philosophy must explicate purpose², be logical, and accord with objective Truth.
3. A good philosophy flows downwards from a grander source of energy, knowledge, or Universal Truth.

MIMS 1.01 - “MIMS” as a MIMS

When we look at this, we can then reverse evaluate the MIMS philosophy itself. Is MIMS a “good philosophy”? Is it even useful?

With regards to internal self-consistence, the MIMS philosophy has been designed to explore concepts as versatile as futurism to anything in the *Extended* portion, to the “Big G”³ and is specifically meant to increase life. Life herein defined as the generative function of living and not merely the act of cellular reproduction and metabolism!

¹ Quick application: drugs which improve health are good, even if they are toxic; drugs which are natural and good become bad if they harm you. If jogging hurts you, it is then a bad philosophy that you need to jog everyday. If jogging saves you from morbid obesity, it is good even if it is hard on your joints. This should be obvious to people, but I'm continually surprised by what needs to be explained to modern humans.

² Not meaning. Meaning comes from the individual's attachment of conscious frameworks to the subject matter.

³

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

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It accomplishes this purpose by bringing to the individual the tools and thoughts (which lead to engineering more tools and technologies) related specifically to enhancing life, particularly future living. It also seeks to be efficient, as well as comprehensive, as a part and parcel of the Extended Plasma-electromagnetic Cosmology. That means no difficult formulae to explain other abstruse formulae. Results interest us, more than the defeat of pedants.

As for explaining a purpose and being logical, this is achieved on a case by case basis. However, I am unaware of any failures of the links of the chain, and therefore, the chain itself seems strong.

As for flowing down from a grander source, this has been provided for in MIMS 1.0 and 1.11⁴, and 1.12⁵. Therefore these results can be presumed to be solid foundations for the remainder of the 1.0x series, as well as working retroactively. So if 1.02 is satisfied, then it seems that 1.01 is also doubly satisfied.

MIMS 1.03 - Introducing Standards

As it happens, today I introduced some paper naming convention standards. It would be a fair thing to explain these, briefly here, as a future reference, by way of discussing the MIMS naming. The Standards are found online at the EPEMC Gateway.⁶ However, in short the MIMS category uses a X.YY.ZZ or X.YYY.ZZ standard (depending on how dynamic a subcategory gets.)

For example this paper cover 1.01, 1.02, and 1.03. 1.0 represents the generation and main topic, which 1.0 is the MIMS itself. Whereas 1.1 series referred to the "Big G" diagram. So 1.11 and 1.12 were the letter about "Big G" and the self-consistency paper themselves. 1.01 refers to the MIMS as a MIMS concept/test. 1.02 refers to the goodness of the philosophy, whose usefulness is derived from its purpose, fulfilling the needs defined in 1.02 for the fulfillment of the goal of 1.01. The fact that this occurred pre-discussion lends power to the concept of the positivity of the philosophy. Comparable to other as-of-yet unassailed philosophies such as Tao or Natural Philosophy (physics). All of these are not inconsistent with MIMS, which provides for a basis of support under the Supreme Sciences framework!

As for the use of .YYY and .ZZ needs, it would be in the following conditions:

- .xY - the second Y, regardless of the first refers to a refinement of the concept
- .xxY - the third Y will refer to a refinement, recursive, to the second Y
- .ZZ will refer to version numbers, as needed
 - They may lead or not lead to a new X. generation number, depending on the judgment of the writer or engineer.

Examples of the latter two points would be as follows:

Animals.Mammals-Apes.homo erectus or Animals.Mammals-Apes-Gorillas would be categorically X.YY.Z and X.YYY respectively.

⁴

https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

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Animals.Mammals-Apes.homosapiens sapiens would be a great example of a X.YY.ZZ arrangement.

Hopefully these generation concepts are not too difficult.

So far as of writing there are only 3 generations (X.):

1. MIMS itself
2. MIMS hypotheticals - “experiments” or “life-labs”
3. Futurism specific topics; usually cross-threaded to some other EPEMC series, which may or may not apply retroactively; example SPACERS papers

According to the site, the standard definitions are:

- PEMC X.Y
- PEMS X.Y
- MIMS X.YY.ZZ
- SS (Strategy Series) X.YY
- SPR (SPACER) X.YY
- KY (Kithiki) X.YY
- AR (Arthwyr/Arthur) X.YY
- DUD (Dark Universe Debunking) X.YY
- ATL (Atlantis) X.Y
- ARC (Archaeology) X.YY.ZZ
- ANT (Anthropology) X.YY.ZZ
- SOC (Sociology) X.Y & C.X.YY.ZZ for Chinese Series

These may be subject to later change, as needed.

The goal of this framework is to enable more individuals to take up the work, to evolve and expand it into new areas, without my oversight. Or else how can EPEMC fulfill its mission and designation as an “open source cosmology”?

This will also enable EPEMC to organizationally surpass the “Standard Model” in all arenas, if not in volume and output, at least in its internal self-consistency! That makes EPEMC also an excellent MIMS...

PEMC 1.01 - Altstream Quality Insurance "Heat test"⁷

There isn't much time to talk about the quality differences in this. A separate 1.011 paper is recommended for discussing the quality of altstream and scientific evidence. The names given here are considered self-evidently high quality altstream work, and high standards. This is merely a "heat test" to indicate to the audience whether or not an altstream research appears to have their work/"stuff" together or not. This is not a peer review, and may be subject to matters of opinion. However, we do not have some kind of standard that enables the improvement of the altstream, if it is to work towards a strategy which actually upseats the corrupt, toxic, polluting, hateful, and destructive - even zealous and dogmatic - mainstream. To help pull out the good and flush away the bad, and to avoid "throwing the baby out with the bathwater."

ALTSTREAM "thermal spectrum" for quality of research, video, or documentary

Sincerely,
 Sf. R. Careaga

⁷ Bear in mind that PEMS, HEGEME, and other series may fall below PEMC 1.1 and 1.2 for example; while some categories will fall under EPEMC and should simply use their category designations, like ATL, ARC, SOC etc. Chinese specific studies should use a C.xx designation if they are not using a MIMS or SS designation primarily. Otherwise, the same rules as MIMS 1.03 states still apply.